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ROSETTA USER MANUAL

by

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<p>SUMMARY: Rosetta is a web application for converting data in ASCII CSV or Excel files to NetCDF format. The conversion is defined in a special file - a template - that defines how (and which parts of) the data file is extracted and converted to spreadsheet NetCDF. If you have several data files formatted in the same way, you can define a conversion template once and reuse it for all of these data files. Rosetta is run in a web browser without installing any plugins. The generated NetCDF file, as well as the generated template, can be downloaded to your computer. Rosetta can be accessed at https://rosetta.nersc.no/</p>	

Rosetta User Manual

19 September 2023

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Overview

Rosetta is a web application for converting data in ASCII CSV or Excel files to NetCDF format. The conversion is defined in a special file - a template - that defines how (and which parts of) the data file is extracted and converted to spreadsheet NetCDF. If you have several data files formatted in the same way, you can define a conversion template once and reuse it for all of these data files. Rosetta is run in a web browser without installing any plugins. The generated NetCDF file, as well as the generated template, can be downloaded to your computer.

Rosetta can be accessed at <https://rosetta.nersc.no/>

Email support: rosetta@nersc.no

Rosetta

This specific version of Rosetta has been tailored for NMDC, NorDataNet and SIOS.

Welcome to Rosetta, a data transformation tool. Rosetta is a web-based service that provides an easy, wizard-based interface for data collectors to transform their datalogger generated ASCII output into Climate and Forecast (CF) compliant netCDF files. These files will contain the metadata describing what data is contained in the file, the instruments used to collect the data, and other critical information that otherwise may be lost in one of many dreaded README files.

In addition, with the understanding that the observational community does appreciate the ease of use of ASCII files, methods for transforming the netCDF back into a user defined CSV or spreadsheet formats is planned to be incorporated into Rosetta.

We hope that Rosetta will be of value to the science community users who have needs for transforming the data they have collected or stored in non-standard formats.

Rosetta is currently under continued further development, and ready for beta testing.

What would you like to do?

Convert a file to the netCDF format and create a new template

Upload, modify, and use an existing template

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Introduction

Major functionality

Rosetta provides two main features:

1. Conversion of an ASCII CSV or Excel spreadsheet file to NetCDF/CF format.
2. Definition and storage of a specification (i.e. a template) of the conversion.

Key concepts

Rosetta handles three categories of data:

1. **Profiles** - a dataset collected at a given location and point in time (i.e. fixed latitude, longitude and time) where the observations are made at different altitudes (i.e. variable altitudes above or depths below sea surface)
2. **Time series** - a dataset collected at a given location and altitude (i.e. fixed latitude, longitude and altitude), where observations are made over a time period (i.e. varying time coordinate)
3. **Trajectories** - a dataset collected over time at a given altitude (i.e. fixed altitude or depth) at a series of locations (i.e. varying latitude, longitude, time coordinates).

For each category of data, Rosetta can handle a number of measured or derived parameters. These are stored in the generated NetCDF file together with the coordinate variables (time, altitude, latitude, longitude), description of every parameter and coordinate (variable metadata) and descriptions of the dataset as a whole and (global metadata)

Known limitations

At present, the size of the input data file is limited to 1.2 MB.

Appendix D shows the supported formats for date and time.

The delimiter characters cannot be mixed between any two columns in a data file. For instance, Rosetta will not accept a combination of comma (‘,’) and whitespace (one or more space ‘ ’) characters in between two columns. Even if the application allows you to check multiple delimiter characters in the “Specify delimiters” screen, only one type of delimiter characters can be used at a time to separate two columns.

Conversion using a predefined template

Step 1: Choose template and data files

From the homepage of Rosetta (<https://rosetta.nersc.no/>) select to start with an existing template by pressing the “Upload, modify and use an existing template” button near the bottom of the page:

What would you like to do?

Convert a file to the netCDF format and create a new template

Upload, modify, and use an existing template

On the new page, click the “Choose file” button. Then select the template file you would like to use from your computer or a network drive, and press the “Upload” button. This will load the definition of the conversion to be performed into Rosetta. After upload is completed, press the “Next” button to proceed with selection of a data file which matches the template. After the data file is successfully uploaded, press “Next” again to move to the next step

Screenshots for uploading files below. (Intermediate screens of uploads completed are left out.)

Rosetta

Rosetta

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Upload Template' step in the Rosetta interface. On the left, a navigation menu lists steps: Upload Template, Upload File, Specify Header Lines, Specify Delimiters, Specify Variable Attributes, Specify Site Specific Information, Specify General Information, Download Converted File, and Publish. The 'Upload Template' step is selected. The main area is titled 'Upload Template' and displays the message 'uak2020_502_converted_average1m-Rosetta_111751.template successfully uploaded' with a 'Clear file upload' button. A 'Next' button is located at the bottom left.

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Upload File' step in the Rosetta interface. The main area is titled 'Upload File' and contains the instruction 'Upload an ASCII file, or an MS Excel 97 (.xls) file. Max file size is 1.2 MB.' Below this is a 'Choose file' button and the text 'No file chosen'. An 'Open' file explorer window is overlaid on the interface, showing the file 'uak2020_502_converted_average1m.cnv' selected. The file explorer shows a table of files:

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
uak2020_502_converted_average1m.cnv	07/10/2020 11:02	CNV File	20 KB
uak2020_502_converted_average1m-Rosetta_111751.template	06/10/2020 13:09	TEMPLATE File	4 KB

The file explorer also shows a search bar, navigation buttons, and a 'File name' field containing 'uak2020_502_converted_average1m.cnv'. 'Open' and 'Cancel' buttons are at the bottom right of the window.

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Upload File' step in the Rosetta interface. The main area is titled 'Upload File' and contains the instruction 'Upload an ASCII file, or an MS Excel 97 (.xls) file. Max file size is 1.2 MB.' Below this is a 'Choose file' button, the text 'uak2020_50...erage1m.cnv', and an 'Upload' button. A 'Previous' button is located at the bottom left.

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Upload File' step in the Rosetta interface. The main area is titled 'Upload File' and contains the instruction 'Upload an ASCII file, or an MS Excel 97 (.xls) file. Max file size is 1.2 MB.' Below this is the message 'uak2020_502_converted_average1m.cnv successfully uploaded' with a 'Clear file upload' button. 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons are located at the bottom left.

After successfully uploading template and data files:

- uak2020_502_converted_average1m-Rosetta_111751.template
- uak2020_502_converted_average1m.cnv

you can proceed by pressing the “Next” button again.

Step 2: Specify which lines in the data file are headerlines

The uploaded template specifies which lines in the data files constitute the header. Typically the header is located in the beginning of the data file, and occupies from a single line to some tens of lines. An empty header is also possible (i.e. all lines in the file contain data). Rosetta shows a screen like below where the header lines are marked, and then the beginning of the data found in the file.

Rosetta

Specify Header Lines

Indicate which lines are header (i.e. not data) lines, or select 'No Header Lines' if there are none.

No header lines available in this file

	Line	Data
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	124	# binavg_omit = 0
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	125	# binavg_min_scans_bin = 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	126	# binavg_max_scans_bin = 2147403647
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	127	# binavg_surface_bin = no, min = 0.000, max = 0.000, value = 0.000
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	128	# file_type = ascii
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	129	*END*
<input type="checkbox"/>	130	2.925704 1.000 2.1877 1.011 1456.18 32.8985 0.0000e+00
<input type="checkbox"/>	131	2.924292 2.000 2.1801 2.021 1456.15 32.8882 0.0000e+00
<input type="checkbox"/>	132	2.923811 3.000 2.1764 3.032 1456.14 32.8855 0.0000e+00
<input type="checkbox"/>	133	2.923709 4.000 2.1744 4.042 1456.15 32.8857 0.0000e+00
<input type="checkbox"/>	134	2.923998 5.000 2.1753 5.053 1456.17 32.8877 0.0000e+00

Quick Save

The header lines are marked a background colour, making it is easy to separate from the lines containing data. Lines holding data are always shown on a white background.

The example used above has many header lines, so you will need to scroll down to see the data lines. In case your data file has more or fewer header lines than specified by the template, you can check or uncheck these lines to either mark them as header lines or include them as data lines. If you modify the number of header lines, you can use the “Quick Save” button to store a copy of your new template. Once you have verified that the header lines are correctly marked up, press “Next” to continue.

Step 3: Specify delimiter and decimal separator

Rosetta accepts different characters as delimiters between the columns in the data lines. The Nansen Center version of Rosetta also accepts comma (“,”) as the decimal separator. You can choose the characters in the screen below. Note that these characters must match the data file uploaded in step 1. As in the previous step, you can “Quick Save” the template if you make any changes. After checking that the given delimiters and decimal separators are correct for your data file, press “Next” to continue to the next step.

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Specify Delimiters' step in the Rosetta interface. On the left is a navigation menu with options: Upload Template, Upload File, Specify Header Lines, Specify Delimiters (selected), Specify Variable Attributes, Specify Site Specific Information, Specify General Information, Download Converted File, and Publish. Below the menu are 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons. The main area is titled 'Specify Delimiters' and contains two sections: 'Please specify delimiter(s) used.' with radio buttons for Tab, Comma, Whitespace (checked), Colon, Semicolon, Single Quote, Double Quote, and Other; and 'Please specify decimal separator used.' with radio buttons for Point (checked) and Comma. A 'Quick Save' button is located below the main area.

Step 4: Specify variables

Rosetta now uses the specification of header lines, delimiter and decimal separators to split the data lines into columns for the variables of the dataset. This split is shown in the following screen:

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Specify Variable Attributes' step in the Rosetta interface. The navigation menu on the left includes: Upload Template, Upload File, Specify Header Lines, Specify Delimiters, Specify Variable Attributes (selected), Specify Site Specific Information, Specify General Information, Download Converted File, and Publish. Below the menu are 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons. The main area is titled 'Specify Variable Attributes' and contains instructions: 'Click on each column and specify the information asked for. Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file. All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.' Below the instructions is a table with 8 columns: a selection column, 'sea_water_e', 'depth', 'sea_water_p', 'sea_water_p', 'speed_of_sc', 'sea_water_p', and 'Do Not Use'. The first column has a green checkmark. The table contains 12 rows of data. A 'Quick Save' button is located below the table.

	sea_water_e	depth	sea_water_p	sea_water_p	speed_of_sc	sea_water_p	Do Not Use
130	2.925704	1.000	2.1877	1.011	1456.18	32.8985	0.0000e+00
131	2.924292	2.000	2.1801	2.021	1456.15	32.8882	0.0000e+00
132	2.923811	3.000	2.1764	3.032	1456.14	32.8855	0.0000e+00
133	2.923709	4.000	2.1744	4.042	1456.15	32.8857	0.0000e+00
134	2.923998	5.000	2.1753	5.053	1456.17	32.8877	0.0000e+00
135	2.923632	6.000	2.1760	6.063	1456.19	32.8818	0.0000e+00
136	2.925519	7.000	2.1729	7.074	1456.22	32.9078	0.0000e+00
137	2.952916	8.000	2.3045	8.084	1457.08	33.1102	0.0000e+00
138	2.955927	9.000	2.3883	9.095	1457.40	33.0597	0.0000e+00
139	2.909928	10.000	2.0544	10.106	1455.65	32.8340	0.0000e+00
140	2.857184	11.000	1.0609	11.116	1451.76	33.2142	0.0000e+00

Since the uploaded template matches the chosen data file, no action is needed here. The template holds the specification of each variable to include in the conversion, and marks those columns that are not converted. In this case, the last data column will not be included in the NetCDF file to be generated in the last step.

Step 5: Specify site specific information

Rosetta lets you specify the name of the site, the location, time and altitude (or depth) where the dataset was collected. This can be given in the following screen.

Rosetta

Upload Template
Upload File
Specify Header Lines
Specify Delimiters
Specify Variable Attributes
Specify Site Specific Information
Specify General Information
Download Converted File
Publish

Specify Site Specific Information

* denotes required field

*Station or Platform Name is a regex
KV_SVALBARD

*Station or Platform Date and Time is a regex
\ System UTC = (d{4})-d{2}

*Station Latitude is a regex
\ NMEA Latitude = (d+\d+ degrees_north

*Station Longitude is a regex
\ NMEA Longitude = (d+\d+ degrees_east

Previous Next

Quick Save

The uploaded template defines the dataset as a profile. This means that the geographical location and time can be given in addition to the name of the site where the data were collected. In this case the site is a vessel, Norwegian Coast Guard vessel KV Svalbard. The remaining site variables, location and time, are read from the header of the data files, using a string matching pattern called a regular expression.

The regular expressions used in this template works like this:

- * Escapes the asterisk to find an actual * symbol.
- () It is the information inside the parentheses that will be included in the NetCDF file.
- \d Represents a number character (i.e. a digit).
- { } Indicates how many times the character in front of it is repeated.
- + Lets the character in front of it repeat 1 or more times.

The Nansen Center Rosetta version has implemented regular expressions as a means to extract descriptive information (i.e. metadata) for a dataset from a data file. This allows a template to be used to automatically extract metadata that will go into the output NetCDF file instead of having to type this information into the screen.

It is also possible to fill in the fields with the actual location and time instead of using regular expressions. This will be preferred if e.g. the text in the header is not in the correct format, if the information is not available in the header, or if the information is the same across all the files you want to use the template for.

Step 6: Specify general information

Additional descriptions (metadata) for the dataset can be given in the screen below. This allows you to specify important information such as

- Title of the dataset
- The data license that you publish the dataset under

- A short summary of the dataset
- Keywords to make it more easily searchable once published in a data repository
- Name and email for the scientists producing and publishing the data
- Name of the organisation (data centre) publishing the data

Note that in this template, some of the mandatory fields are filled with dummy values. This includes, among others, the names and emails of publishers and contributors. The reason for this was the template was created for use in a research school where different students contributed to collecting different CTD stations together with the course instructors. The use of dummy values showed the students where they needed to fill in information when they prepared the data for publication after the fieldwork had been completed.

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the 'Specify General Information' section of the Rosetta interface. On the left is a navigation menu with options like 'Upload Template', 'Specify General Information', and 'Publish'. The main area contains a form with the following fields:

- Title:** CTD station collected in Storfjorden, Svalban
- License:** CC-BY
- Naming Authority:** no.nersc.uak
- ID:** UAK2020-CTD-20200623-Station-502
- ISO Topic Category:** oceans
- Keywords Vocabulary:** GCMD Science Keywords
- Keywords:** EARTH SCIENCE, OCEANS, OCEAN TEMF
- Data Assembly Center:** NERSC
- Processing Level:** Unknown
- Publisher Name:** Unknown
- Publisher Email:** Unknown
- Contributor Name:** Unknown
- Contributor Email:** Unknown
- Contributor Role:** (empty)
- Publisher Url:** https://www.nersc.no/

At the bottom left of the form area are 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons.

Once you have filled in the remaining descriptions in this screen, press “Next” to go to the final step of the conversion.

Note: If you have a template where all needed information is filled in, you still have to place your cursor in one of the fields and then move it to another field to enable the “Next” button. For instance, pressing the Tab key will move the cursor to the next field.

Step 7: Download resulting files

Using the template and the additional information provided in steps 2-6, Rosetta can now convert the input data file into a NetCDF file. After the conversion is completed, you can download the generated NetCDF file and the updated template file from the screen below.

Rosetta

Upload Template
Upload File
Specify Header Lines
Specify Delimiters
Specify Variable Attributes
Specify Site Specific Information
Specify General Information
Download Converted File
Publish

Download Converted File

- [netCDF Data File](#)
- [uak2020_502_converted_average1m-Rosetta_2021-03-03_155116.template](#)

Previous Next

Quick Save

The template can be reused to convert other data files with the same structure for header and data lines. This will save time for later conversions.

Creating your own template

If no predefined template fits your ASCII data file, you can create a new template.

This section shows you how to create a template for a time series of observations from a meteorological station. The beginning of the ASCII data file is as follows:

```
Filnavn:Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv
Lat:60.38
Lon:05.33
Area:Florida-Bergen-Norge
Dato,,id,Solskinstid,Lufttemperatur,"Relativ luftfuktighet",Vindretning,Vindstyrke
2019-11-01,00:00:00,0,5,9999.99,161,2.3
2019-11-01,00:10:00,0,5.1,9999.99,158,2.6
2019-11-01,00:20:00,0,5.1,9999.99,169,2.8
2019-11-01,00:30:00,0,5.1,9999.99,163,2.3
2019-11-01,00:40:00,0,5.1,9999.99,159,2.2
2019-11-01,00:50:00,0,5.1,9999.99,164,1.8
2019-11-01,01:00:00,0,5.1,9999.99,166,2.5
2019-11-01,01:10:00,0,5,9999.99,154,2.2
2019-11-01,01:20:00,0,5,9999.99,161,2
2019-11-01,01:30:00,0,5,9999.99,155,2
...
```

This input file has seven data columns separated by comma (‘,’). The first two columns (numbered 0 and 1 by Rosetta) contain the date and time of day (UTC) of the observation. The next five columns contain the number of seconds of sunshine on this date, air temperature, relative humidity, wind direction and wind strength.

Step 1: Choose to create a new template

From the homepage of Rosetta (<https://rosetta.nersc.no/>) select to create a new template by pressing the “Convert a file to the netCDF format and create a new template” button near the bottom of the page:

What would you like to do?

Step 2: Select the observation platform that collected your data

From the screen below, select the observation platform for your data. Then press the “Next” button to move to the next step.

Rosetta

The screenshot shows the Rosetta web interface for selecting an observation platform. On the left, a sidebar lists steps: Select Observation Platform (active), Upload File, Specify Header Lines, Specify Delimiters, Specify Variable Attributes, Specify Site Specific Information, Specify General Information, and Download Converted File. A 'Next' button is at the bottom of the sidebar. The main area is titled 'Select Observation Platform' and contains six radio button options, each with a small image and text: 'Single Station or Tower (timeSeries)' (selected), 'Moored Buoy (profile)', 'Radiosonde (trajectory)', 'Wind Profiler (profile)', 'Aircraft (trajectory)', and 'Single CTD/XBT cast (profile)'.

The difference between the observation platforms are:

Timeseries:

- Constant Longitude, Latitude and Altitude.
- Time is the coordinate variable.

Profile:

- Constant Longitude, Latitude and Time.

- Altitude is the coordinate variable.

Trajectory:

- Constant Altitude.
- Longitude, Latitude and Time are coordinate variables.

Values for the constants are specified in Step 7: Specify site specific information.

Values for each coordinate variable that vary, must be given in one of the columns in the input data file.

Step 3: Upload your data file

Select the data file by pressing the “Choose file” button and navigate to where it is located on your computer or network drive. Then press the “Upload” to let Rosetta read the data file into memory, and then press “Next” to continue with creating a new template.

Screenshots from the upload process:

Rosetta

Rosetta

Rosetta

Select Observation Platform

Upload File

Specify Header Lines

Specify Delimiters

Specify Variable Attributes

Specify Site Specific Information

Specify General Information

Download Converted File

Upload File

Upload an ASCII file, or an MS Excel 97 (.xls) file. Max file size is 1.2 MB.

Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916-3.csv successfully uploaded [Clear file upload](#)

[Previous](#) [Next](#)

Step 4: Define header lines

The next screen allows you to mark the header lines of the data files just loaded. Check each line that Rosetta should skip when looking for data. If every line of the data file contains data values, press the “No header lines available in this file” option. When header lines are defined, press “Next” to continue with template definition.

Screenshots from defining the header of the data file:

Rosetta

Select Observation Platform

Upload File

Specify Header Lines

Specify Delimiters

Specify Variable Attributes

Specify Site Specific Information

Specify General Information

Download Converted File

Specify Header Lines

Indicate which lines are header (i.e. not data) lines, or select 'No Header Lines' if there are none.

No header lines available in this file

Line	Data
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Filnavn:Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lat:60.38
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lon:05.33
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Area:Florida-Bergen-Norge
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dato,,id,Solskinstid,Lufttemperatur,"Relativ Luftfuktighet",Vindretning,Vindstyrke
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019-11-01,00:00:00,0,5,9999.99,161,2.3
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019-11-01,00:10:00,0,5,1,9999.99,158,2.6
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019-11-01,00:20:00,0,5,1,9999.99,169,2.8
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019-11-01,00:30:00,0,5,1,9999.99,163,2.3
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019-11-01,00:40:00,0,5,1,9999.99,159,2.2
<input type="checkbox"/>	2019-11-01,00:50:00,0,5,1,9999.99,164,1.8

[Previous](#) [Next](#)

[Quick Save](#)

If you want to store the part of the template defined so far, press “Quick Save” before moving on.

Step 5: Specify delimiter and decimal separator

To be able to split the data lines into columns, and convert the text strings representing data values into numeric or time variables, Rosetta needs to know what characters are used to delimit columns and which is used as a decimal separator. Select from the screen shown below and the press “Next” to continue to the next step.

Rosetta

Specify Delimiters

Please specify delimiter(s) used.

Tab Comma Whitespace Colon

Semicolon Single Quote Double Quote Other

Please specify decimal separator used.

Point Comma

Previous Next

Quick Save

Step 6: Specify variables

Using the provided separators Rosetta split each data line into columns and displays the first lines in the screen shown below. To begin with, these columns are given dummy names such as “column 0”, “column 1” and so on. As you begin to define what parameters are found in the file, the columns will be renamed accordingly.

In the data file above the columns contain the following:

- Column 0: date of measurement, formatted as yyyy-MM-dd
- Column 1: time of day, formatted as HH:mm:ss
- Column 2: seconds of sunshine that day, a floating point value
- Column 3: air temperature, a floating point value
- Column 4: relative humidity, a floating point value
- Column 5: wind direction in degrees (relative to north), a floating point value
- Column 6: wind speed, a floating point value

We want to include five of these columns in the output NetCDF file, and show the definition of a few of these below. The remaining two columns will be skipped, which we indicate by checking the “Do not use this column of data” option in the “Enter variable attributes” screen.

To define the content of “column 0”, click on its name in the table header, check the “Assign a variable name” option in the “Enter Variable Attributes” screen and fill in the chosen name (in our case “date”). The variable name has to match one of the alternatives that pops up when you start to write. Then press the Tab key to register your choice. This will open the next part of the screen.

This column defines the time axis of the data, so check “Yes” for “Is this column a coordinate variable?” and select the appropriate type (“Date only (year, month, and/or day”). Next, select “Text” as the data type and enter the required metadata for the variable. All required metadata elements are marked with a red asterisk “*” in Rosetta. For units, enter the string “yyyy-MM-dd” (without quotes!) or check the “show unit builder” option to get a list of allowed values for a unit for this variable. When you have finished, press “Done” to get back to the table. Now

you will see that the column you just defined has changed name and been given a green checkmark to indicate that it is fully defined in the template.

Once a variable has been successfully defined, you will see a checkbox with the label “use metadata from another column?” when opening subsequent columns. Only click this option if you already have filled in a column of the same type because it will use all the input from the column you choose to copy from.

To define the content of “column 3”, click on its name in the table header, check the “Assign a variable name” option and fill in the chosen name (in our case “air_temperature”). This column is not a coordinate variable so we check “No” for the question “Is this column a coordinate variable?”. This column contains floating point values, so check “Float (decimal)” for data type. Then fill the required metadata. The correct string for units is “degree_C” (without the quotes); this string can be entered by hand or copied from the unit builder by checking this and selecting from a list of allowed values for air temperature.

After defining the remaining three columns we want to include in the output NetCDF file, the table header should contain green tick marks for all columns, and we can press “Next” to get to the next step of the conversion process. (The columns that we wanted to skip are named “Do Not Use” in the table.)

Screenshots from the process of specifying variables:

Rosetta

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for.
Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file.
All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

	column 0	column 1	column 2	column 3	column 4	column 5	column 6
?	?Filename:Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv						
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2.3
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00	0	5.1	9999.99	158	2.6
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00	0	5.1	9999.99	169	2.8
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00	0	5.1	9999.99	163	2.3
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00	0	5.1	9999.99	159	2.2
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00	0	5.1	9999.99	164	1.8
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00	0	5.1	9999.99	166	2.5
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00	0	5	9999.99	154	2.2
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00	0	5	9999.99	155	2
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00	0	4.9	9999.99	148	1.9

Quick Save

Quick Save

Enter Variable Attributes ✕

Questions or comments
Version : 1.1.3-NERSC
Build Date: 2022-01-08

What would you like to do with this column of data?

Assign a variable name Do not use this column of data

use metadata from another column?

Is this variable a coordinate variable? (examples: latitude, longitude, time)

Yes No

What type of coordinate variable?

Specify variable data type:

Integer Float (decimal) Text

Required Metadata:

Variable Description

Units

show unit builder

Recommended Metadata:

CF Name

Additional Metadata:

done

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ **Specify Variable Attributes**
- ▶ Specify Site Specific Information
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ Download Converted File

Previous
Next

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for. Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file. All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

#	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> column 0: <input type="checkbox"/> column 1	<input type="checkbox"/> column 2	<input type="checkbox"/> column 3	<input type="checkbox"/> column 4	<input type="checkbox"/> column 5	<input type="checkbox"/> column 6
0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ?Filnavn: F column 0: date	<input type="checkbox"/> 01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv				
5	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 00:00:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 161
6	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 00:10:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5.1	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 158
7	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 00:20:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5.1	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 169
8	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 00:30:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5.1	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 163
9	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 00:40:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5.1	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 159
10	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 00:50:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5.1	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 164
11	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 01:00:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5.1	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 166
12	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 01:10:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 154
13	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 01:20:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 161
14	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 01:30:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 155
15	<input type="checkbox"/> 2019-11-01	<input type="checkbox"/> 01:40:00	<input type="checkbox"/> 0	<input type="checkbox"/> 4.9	<input type="checkbox"/> 9999.99	<input type="checkbox"/> 148

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the info. Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file. All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

	column 0: d	column 1: t
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00

Enter Variable Attributes

What would you like to do with this column of data?

Assign a variable name Do not use this column of data

time

Use metadata from another column?

Is this variable a coordinate variable? (examples: latitude, longitude, time)

Yes No

What type of coordinate variable?

Time only (hour, minute, second, and/or millisecond) v

Specify variable data type:

Integer Float (decimal) Text

Required Metadata:

Variable Description: Time of measurement

Units: HH:mm:ss

show unit builder

What type of data are we building units for?

time only v

unit prefix: v unit: HH:mm:ss v + -

Recommended Metadata:

CF Name: time

Additional Metadata:

+ - Calendar Type v

done cancel

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ **Specify Variable Attributes**
- ▶ Specify Site Specific Information
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ Download Converted File

Previous Next

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for. Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file. All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

	column 0: d	column 1: t	column 2: u	column 3: w	column 4: s	column 5: p	column 6: r
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2.3
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00	0	5.1	9999.99	158	2.6
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00	0	5.1	9999.99	169	2.8
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00	0	5.1	9999.99	163	2.3
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00	0	5.1	9999.99	159	2.2
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00	0	5.1	9999.99	164	1.8
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00	0	5.1	9999.99	166	2.5
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00	0	5	9999.99	154	2.2
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00	0	5	9999.99	155	2
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00	0	4.9	9999.99	148	1.9

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for.
Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file.
All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

	column 0: d	column 1: t	column 2	column 3	column 4	column 5	column 6
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00	0				
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00	0				
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00	0				
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00	0				
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00	0				
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00	0				
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00	0	5.1	9999.99	166	2.5
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00	0	5	9999.99	154	2.2
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00	0	5	9999.99	155	2
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00	0	4.9	9999.99	148	1.9

Enter Variable Attributes

What would you like to do with this column of data?

Assign a variable name
 Do not use this column of data

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ **Specify Variable Attributes**
- ▶ Specify Site Specific Information
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ Download Converted File

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for.
Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file.
All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

	column 0: d	column 1: t	column 2: f	column 3	column 4	column 5	column 6
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00	0	column 2: Do Not Use	9999.99	161	2.3
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00	0	5.1	9999.99	138	2.6
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00	0	5.1	9999.99	169	2.8
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00	0	5.1	9999.99	163	2.3
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00	0	5.1	9999.99	159	2.2
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00	0	5.1	9999.99	164	1.8
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00	0	5.1	9999.99	166	2.5
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00	0	5	9999.99	154	2.2
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00	0	5	9999.99	155	2
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00	0	4.9	9999.99	148	1.9

Enter Variable Attributes ✕

What would you like to do with this column of data?

Assign a variable name Do not use this column of data

air_temperature

use metadata from another column?

Is this variable a coordinate variable? (examples: latitude, longitude, time)

Yes No

Specify variable data type:

Integer Float (decimal) Text

Required Metadata:

Instrument Description

Missing Value

Variable Description

Units

show unit builder

Recommended Metadata:

Instrument Height (negative for depths)

Instrument Height Unit

Maximum Value (Calibrated)

Minimum Value (Calibrated)

CF Name

Additional Metadata:

+ - Calibration Range

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ **Specify Variable Attributes**
- ▶ Specify Site Specific Information
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ Download Converted File

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for. Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file. All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> column 0: d	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> column 1: t	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> column 2: D	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> column 3: a	<input type="checkbox"/> column 4	<input type="checkbox"/> column 5	<input type="checkbox"/> column 6
	?Filnavn:Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv						
				column 3: air_temperature			
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00	0	5	9999.99	158	2.3
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00	0	5.1	9999.99	158	2.6
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00	0	5.1	9999.99	169	2.8
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00	0	5.1	9999.99	163	2.3
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00	0	5.1	9999.99	159	2.2
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00	0	5.1	9999.99	164	1.8
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00	0	5.1	9999.99	166	2.5
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00	0	5	9999.99	154	2.2
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00	0	5	9999.99	155	2
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00	0	4.9	9999.99	148	1.9

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ **Specify Variable Attributes**
- ▶ Specify Site Specific Information
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ Download Converted File

Previous
Next

Specify Variable Attributes

Click on each column and specify the information asked for.
Specify 'Do not use this column of data' for all columns that are not to be saved in the netCDF file.
All columns must have a green tickmark before you can continue.

#	column 0: d	column 1: t	column 2: D	column 3: a	column 4: D	column 5: w	column 6: w
?Filnavn:Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv							
5	2019-11-01	00:00:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2.3
6	2019-11-01	00:10:00	0	5.1	9999.99	158	2.6
7	2019-11-01	00:20:00	0	5.1	9999.99	169	2.8
8	2019-11-01	00:30:00	0	5.1	9999.99	163	2.3
9	2019-11-01	00:40:00	0	5.1	9999.99	159	2.2
10	2019-11-01	00:50:00	0	5.1	9999.99	164	1.8
11	2019-11-01	01:00:00	0	5.1	9999.99	166	2.5
12	2019-11-01	01:10:00	0	5	9999.99	154	2.2
13	2019-11-01	01:20:00	0	5	9999.99	161	2
14	2019-11-01	01:30:00	0	5	9999.99	155	2
15	2019-11-01	01:40:00	0	4.9	9999.99	148	1.9

Step 7: Specify site specific information

Our data file contains a time series of meteorological observations. Hence, the site specific information to provide is the name of the site (i.e. the station name) and its location (latitude and longitude, in decimal degrees). The latter information is found in the header of the data file, so we can use two regular expressions to extract the location from the file. These regular expressions are:

- Lat:(\d+\.\d+)
- Lon:(\d+\.\d+)

The name of the site we enter as a string. The altitude of the weather station has been extracted from the meteorological station's web page.

Screen for specifying the site information:

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ Specify Variable Attributes
- ▶ **Specify Site Specific Information**
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ Download Converted File

Previous
Next

Specify Site Specific Information

*** denotes required field**

*Station or Platform Name

is a regex

*Latitude is a regex

*Altitude

is a regex

*Longitude is a regex

Alternative without regular expressions:

The values for Latitude and Longitude must be in the decimal degrees.

For Profile datasets, the date and time must be in ISO 8601 format. E.g. 2017-06-30T13:23:00Z or 2017-06-30.

Step 8: Specify general information

Additional descriptions (metadata) for the dataset can be given in the screen below. This allows you to specify important information such as

- Title of the dataset
- The data license that you publish the dataset under
- A short summary of the dataset
- Keywords to make it more easily searchable once published in a data repository
- Name and email for the scientists producing and publishing the data
- Name of the organisation (data centre) publishing the data

The text strings (or regular expressions) that are specified in these fields will be included in the new template, and used to fill the corresponding metadata elements in the output NetCDF file. All mandatory fields are marked with a red asterisk (*). When all mandatory fields are filled, the “Next” button is enabled. Press this button and you proceed to the next step, which performs the conversion.

Screenshot for general information:

Specify General Information

* denotes required field

* Title [?](#)

is a regex

Florida (Bergen) weather station data Nov-Dec 2019

* License [?](#)

is a regex

NLOD

* Naming Authority [?](#)

is a regex

no.uib.gfi

* ID [?](#)

is a regex

Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916

* ISO Topic Category [?](#)

climatologyMeteorologyAtmosphere [v](#)

* Keywords Vocabulary [?](#)

GCMD Science Keywords [v](#)

* Keywords [?](#)

is a regex

Bergen Florida wind temperature

* Data Assembly Center [?](#)

is a regex

Geofysisk intitutt (UIB)

* Summary [?](#)

Data from met station at Florida in Bergen, Norway, during November and December in 2019.

* Processing Level [?](#)

3

* Publisher Name [?](#)

is a regex

Geofysisk intitutt (UIB)

Publisher Email [?](#)

is a regex

Contributor Name [?](#)

is a regex

Contributor Email [?](#)

is a regex

Contributor Role [?](#)

is a regex

Publisher Url [?](#)

is a regex

Related Url [?](#)

is a regex

Data Set Language [?](#)

is a regex

Platform [?](#)

is a regex

Source [?](#)

is a regex

Project [?](#)

is a regex

Citation [?](#)

History [?](#)

is a regex

Data Set Progress [?](#)

is a regex

References [?](#)

is a regex

Comment [?](#)

is a regex

Step 9: Download resulting files

This step uses the newly created template and converts the chosen columns of the ASCII data file to NetCDF format and adds the specified metadata. When conversion is completed Rosetta presents two download links allowing you to download the generated files.

Screenshot for NetCDF and template file download:

Rosetta

- ▶ Select Observation Platform
- ▶ Upload File
- ▶ Specify Header Lines
- ▶ Specify Delimiters
- ▶ Specify Variable Attributes
- ▶ Specify Site Specific Information
- ▶ Specify General Information
- ▶ **Download Converted File**

Download Converted File

- netCDF Data File
- Florida 2019-11-01 2020-01-31 1580479916-3-Rosetta 2021-03-18 200839.template

Previous

Resources

Sample templates and ASCII data files are available from <https://tinyurl.com/Rosetta-NERSC>

Summary

Rosetta enables you to convert ASCII CSV or Excel spreadsheet files to NetCDF, without having to write a single line of code. You can use a predefined template or make your own to specify how and what parts of the data file should be included in the generated NetCDF file. A template can be reused to convert other data files with the same structure, or used as the basis for making a new template to convert data files with a similar structure. Additional descriptions (e.g. site metadata) can be added interactively or extracted from the header of the input data file. For the latter, Rosetta uses string pattern matching techniques (regular expressions) to automatically extract e.g. geographic positions or date and times from the header of the data file.

Acknowledgements

The Rosetta conversion tool was originally developed by the Unidata Community Program managed by the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR), which operates the National Center for Atmospheric Research in the US. The development of Rosetta at the Nansen Center has been supported by the Research Council of Norway projects Norwegian Marine Data Centre (NMDC) (project no. 208849) and Norwegian Scientific Data Network (NorDataNet) (project no. 245967). Other research projects have contributed to Rosetta development by providing example data files and giving feedback on the implemented functionality, among others, Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System – Knowledge Centre (SIOS -KC) (project no. 291644), Useful Arctic Knowledge - Partnership for Research and Education (UAK) (project nr. 274891), and Integrated Arctic Observation System (INTAROS) (Grant Agreement no. 727890).

References

Unidata, 2021. Rosetta format conversion tool, <https://doi.org/10.5065/D6N878N2>.

Appendix A Example files for profile data

The following snippet shows a .cnv file containing CTD data collected by a Seabird SBE 19plus V2 sensor, quality controlled and averaged to 2 meter intervals.

```
* Sea-Bird SBE 19plus V2 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Documents and Settings\Administrator\Desktop\UAK2020\uak2020_502.hex
* Software Version Seasave V 7.26.7.110
* Temperature SN = 6579
* Conductivity SN = 6579
* System UpLoad Time = Jan 06 1980 15:00:22
* NMEA Latitude = 76.6462
* NMEA Longitude = 19.4062
...
** Ship: KV_SVALBARD
** Cruise: UAK 2020
** Station: 502
** Depth: 198
** Operator: TSS
* Real-Time Sample Interval = 0.2500 seconds
* System UTC = 2020-06-23T10:38:00Z
# nquan = 7
# nvalues = 188
# units = specified
# name 0 = c0S/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = depSM: Depth [salt water, m], lat = 76.00
# name 2 = potemp090C: Potential Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 3 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 4 = svCM: Sound Velocity [Chen-Millero, m/s]
# name 5 = sal00: Salinity, Practical [PSU]
# name 6 = flag: flag
# span 0 = 2.756824, 2.974668
# span 1 = 1.000, 188.000
# span 2 = -1.8962, 2.3883
# span 3 = 1.011, 190.069
# span 4 = 1442.56, 1457.40
# span 5 = 32.8340, 35.3753
```

```

# span 6 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = meters: 1
# start_time = Jun 23 2020 10:38:00 [System UTC, header]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
...
# binavg_min_scans_bin = 1
# binavg_max_scans_bin = 2147483647
# binavg_surface_bin = no, min = 0.000, max = 0.000, value = 0.000
# file_type = ascii
*END*
  2.925704      1.000      2.1877      1.011      1456.18      32.8985 0.0000e+00
  2.924292      2.000      2.1801      2.021      1456.15      32.8882 0.0000e+00
  2.923811      3.000      2.1764      3.032      1456.14      32.8855 0.0000e+00
  2.923709      4.000      2.1744      4.042      1456.15      32.8857 0.0000e+00
  2.923998      5.000      2.1753      5.053      1456.17      32.8877 0.0000e+00
...

```

This data file can be downloaded from [Rosetta-NERSC-Resources](#) in a folder named Seabird_CTD. A template that can be used to convert this ASCII data file to NetCDF is found at [Rosetta-NERSC-Resources](#) in a folder named Seabird_CTD.

Appendix B Example files for time series data

The following snippet shows a CSV file with observations from the Florida meteorological station at the Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen, Norway. Data were downloaded from <https://veret.gfi.uib.no/?action=download>.

```

Filnavn:Florida_2019-11-01_2020-01-31_1580479916.csv
Lat:60.38
Lon:05.33
Area:Florida-Bergen-Norge
Dato,tid,Solskinstid,Lufttemperatur,"Relativ luftfuktighet",Vindretning,Vindstyrke
2019-11-01,00:00:00,0,5,9999.99,161,2.3
2019-11-01,00:10:00,0,5.1,9999.99,158,2.6
2019-11-01,00:20:00,0,5.1,9999.99,169,2.8
2019-11-01,00:30:00,0,5.1,9999.99,163,2.3
2019-11-01,00:40:00,0,5.1,9999.99,159,2.2

```

2019-11-01,00:50:00,0,5.1,9999.99,164,1.8
2019-11-01,01:00:00,0,5.1,9999.99,166,2.5
2019-11-01,01:10:00,0,5,9999.99,154,2.2
2019-11-01,01:20:00,0,5,9999.99,161,2
2019-11-01,01:30:00,0,5,9999.99,155,2
2019-11-01,01:40:00,0,4.9,9999.99,148,1.9
2019-11-01,01:50:00,0,4.9,9999.99,157,2.2
2019-11-01,02:00:00,0,4.9,9999.99,161,2.3
2019-11-01,02:10:00,0,5,9999.99,163,2.3
2019-11-01,02:20:00,0,5.1,9999.99,171,2.3
2019-11-01,02:30:00,0,5.3,9999.99,174,2.8
2019-11-01,02:40:00,0,5.4,9999.99,159,2
2019-11-01,02:50:00,0,5.4,9999.99,165,2.3
2019-11-01,03:00:00,0,5.3,9999.99,165,3
2019-11-01,03:10:00,0,5.2,9999.99,173,2.8
2019-11-01,03:20:00,0,5.4,9999.99,171,3.1
2019-11-01,03:30:00,0,5.3,9999.99,167,2.1
2019-11-01,03:40:00,0,5.5,9999.99,171,2.3
2019-11-01,03:50:00,0,5.5,9999.99,168,2.5
2019-11-01,04:00:00,0,5.5,100,169,2.9
2019-11-01,04:10:00,0,5.4,99,178,3.4
2019-11-01,04:20:00,0,5.2,100,182,2.4
2019-11-01,04:30:00,0,5.2,9999.99,180,2.2
2019-11-01,04:40:00,0,5.1,9999.99,163,2.2
2019-11-01,04:50:00,0,5.1,9999.99,143,2.2
2019-11-01,05:00:00,0,5.4,99,162,3
2019-11-01,05:10:00,0,5.5,97,156,3.2
2019-11-01,05:20:00,0,5.4,96,152,3
2019-11-01,05:30:00,0,5.6,94,154,3.7
2019-11-01,05:40:00,0,5.5,93,154,3.3
2019-11-01,05:50:00,0,5.6,92,178,4.1
2019-11-01,06:00:00,0,5.6,90,174,4.6
2019-11-01,06:10:00,0,5.6,91,171,4.6
2019-11-01,06:20:00,0,5.4,92,160,4.3
2019-11-01,06:30:00,0,5.3,92,161,4.5
2019-11-01,06:40:00,0,5.4,92,159,4.6

2019-11-01,06:50:00,0,5.5,89,152,4.6
 2019-11-01,07:00:00,0,5.5,89,152,4.3
 2019-11-01,07:10:00,0,5.2,91,158,4
 2019-11-01,07:20:00,0,5,93,162,3.7
 ...

This data file and a template that can be used for conversion can be downloaded from [Rosetta-
NERSC-Resources](#) in a folder named MetStation_Florida.

Appendix C Example files for trajectory data

The following snippet of a CSV file with data collected by an unmanned surface vessel called a SailBuoy, from a field experiment in the Fram Strait in summer 2016.

```
% Seaguard II Product number 5650 Serial number 1801. On SailBuoy ?SB Iskant? deployed
in Fram Strait 2016.

% Rec.Year Hour Record Number CO2 optode # 69 #69 #69 #69 #69 #69
#69 #69 #69 #69 Conductivity sensor #1376 #1376 #1376 #1376
#1376 Optode sensor #2537 #2537 #2537 Optode sensor #2551 #2551 #2551 pH
Optode 5499#37 5499#37 System Par. System Par.

% Rec.Year Hour Record Number pCO2[uatm] CO2[mg/l] Temperature[Deg.C]
CalPhase[Deg] DPhase[Deg] C1RPh[Deg] C2RPh[Deg] C1Amp[mV] C2Amp[mV]
RawTemp[mV] Conductivity[mS/cm] Temperature[Deg.C] Salinity[PSU]
Density[kg/m3] Soundspeed[m/s] O2Concentration[uM] AirSaturation[%]
Temperature[Deg.C] O2Concentration[uM] AirSaturation[%] Temperature[Deg.C]
pH Temperature[Deg.C] GPS Latitude[Deg] GPS Longitude[Deg]

30.06.2016 20:40:00 6 489.9681.367999 5.265263 31.39719
31.39719 64.20319 32.806 389.075 513.9634 611.1559 33.12206
5.41011 34.19186 1026.987 1471.365 398.479 100.6301 5.283304
388.5434 98.63229 5.486095 7.018903 5.262424 77.99095
3.181263

30.06.2016 20:50:00 7 469.0541 1.308763 5.282877 31.12162
31.12162 63.93534 32.81372 390.5771 513.9194 610.6235
33.14514 5.324608 34.30579 1027.087 1471.165 398.0173
100.5288 5.289223 389.0276 98.67171 5.453039 7.439208
5.280493 77.99055 3.191327

30.06.2016 21:00:00 8 460.9776 1.285676 5.294542 31.01051
31.01051 63.81671 32.8062 390.9192 513.8643 610.2708
33.24416 5.316055 34.42833 1027.185 1471.286 396.8074
100.2513 5.300133 389.012 98.68472 5.459761 7.499966
5.292583 77.99001 3.201878

30.06.2016 21:10:00 9 464.2966 1.293792 5.318565 31.04537
31.04537 63.85447 32.8091 391.0192 513.7015 609.5444
33.27413 5.316055 34.46277 1027.212 1471.33 395.6103
100.006 5.322386 388.5174 98.6216 5.484468 7.512468 5.316317
77.98944 3.211182
```

30.06.2016	21:20:00	10	461.3003	1.284232	5.344294	30.99577
	30.99577	63.80964	32.81387	390.7969	513.5674	608.7663
	33.29895	5.328033	34.47895	1027.224	1471.399	395.3341
	99.98319	5.340738	388.9698	98.65065	5.450502	7.528384
	5.342283	77.98876	3.220687			
30.06.2016	21:30:00	11	461.5434	1.284855.345528	30.99853	
	30.99853	63.80807	32.80954	391.0323	513.4227	608.7289
	33.34467	5.350273	34.50854	1027.245	1471.526	394.5273
	99.79166	5.345636	388.9748	98.60802	5.433096	7.539204
	5.344091	77.98813.23087				
30.06.2016	21:40:00	12	461.0642	1.284667	5.321012	31.00154
	31.00154	63.81398	32.81244	390.5168	513.6245	609.4705
	33.35756	5.319489	34.55513	1027.285	1471.461	395.7533
	100.0234	5.315092	389.30998.60985	5.400303	7.538395	
	5.317787	77.98846	3.245447			
30.06.2016	21:50:00	13	454.9571.281549	5.024206	31.0331	31.0331
	63.81392	32.78082	390.4458	515.4869	618.4335	33.17656
	5.062538	34.61255	1027.361	1470.495	404.0652	101.3898
	5.034569	390.1268	98.635 5.328398	7.545804	5.022024	
	77.98921	3.257905				
30.06.2016	22:00:00	14	451.0114	1.273734.953966	31.00669	
	31.00669	63.79381	32.78712	390.5508	515.5406	620.5507
	33.16626	5.093399	34.56861027.323	1470.564	403.0811	
	101.1635	5.042488	390.8219	98.60456	5.247053	7.545156
	4.947441	77.98887	3.267775			
30.06.2016	22:10:00	15	453.7019	1.277775	5.029291	31.01432
	31.01432	63.79123	32.77691	390.8596	515.6187	618.2801
	33.16979	5.007637	34.66184	1027.406	1470.334	407.1436
	102.1033	5.012196	390.9528	98.58065	5.224575	7.556883
	5.032427	77.98843.273687				
30.06.2016	22:20:00	16	426.8588	1.212774.791449	30.73537	
	30.73537	63.49145	32.75608	392.0937	517.1923	625.4441
	32.99825	4.8290134.64877	1027.417	1469.59418.2342	104.3086	
	4.799192	391.8062	98.59593	5.145813	7.557014.789618	
	77.98972	3.285247				
30.06.2016	22:30:00	17	428.0244	1.215877	4.795938	30.75008
	30.75008	63.51055	32.76047	391.8707	517.1356	625.309
	32.99034	4.808372	34.66111	1027.429	1469.522	419.5575
	104.6409	4.80003392.7053	98.57622	5.049099	7.565363	
	4.793711	77.99033.296528				
30.06.2016	22:40:00	18	427.5335	1.213138	4.825987	30.73169
	30.73169	63.49197	32.76029	392.1042	516.959624.4048	
	33.01128	4.827293	34.66574	1027.431469.605	418.5255	
	104.4574	4.827374	393.3568	98.61485	5.000025	7.572043
	4.824236	77.99181	3.307652			
30.06.2016	22:50:00	19	425.7151	1.206877	4.850676	30.69656
	30.69656	63.45789	32.76134	392.2543	516.6379	623.6617
	33.02962	4.8496434.66377	1027.426	1469.693	417.306104.2228	
	4.853235	393.3505	98.60178	4.995514	7.574779	4.848297
	77.99421	3.315795				
30.06.2016	23:00:00	20	431.6272	1.220974.909824	30.75713	
	30.75713	63.52243	32.7653391.677516.2448	621.8806	33.0755	
	4.908058	34.65616	1027.413	1469.922	415.4022	103.9058

4.912235	393.3346	98.56558	4.982847	7.583844	4.907745	
77.99483	3.327235					
30.06.2016	23:10:00	21	432.0412	1.219992	4.957491	30.74467
30.74467	63.52188		32.77721	391.765	516.0535	620.4445
33.11085	4.942413		34.6614	1027.414	1470.069	413.9754
103.6734	4.958746		393.4167	98.52766	4.959871	7.580613
4.955214	77.99739		3.335092			
30.06.2016	23:20:00	22	432.6718	1.220666	4.982155	30.74403
30.74403	63.51588		32.77184	391.9126	515.7735	619.7012
33.13191	4.988754		34.63756	1027.389	1470.227	412.3542
103.3473	4.98871	393.9305	98.59568	4.936054	7.578448	
4.98041	77.99919	3.338833				
30.06.2016	23:30:00	23	431.4367	1.218943	4.942936	30.74178
30.74178	63.50959		32.76781	391.3005	515.9627	620.8831
33.11352	4.957863		34.6484	1027.401	1470.115	412.2912
103.2319	4.95133	393.7526	98.5284	4.927113	7.584423	4.940372
78.00155	3.324332					
30.06.2016	23:40:00	24	435.3734	1.231664	4.907658	30.8102
30.8102	63.58142		32.77122	391.1663	516.2208	621.9459
33.09903	4.921806		34.66917	1027.422	1469.995	412.8964
103.2953	4.918356		394.5448	98.57632	4.868181	7.58095
4.905445	78.00131		3.314612			
30.06.2016	23:50:00	25	454.3575	1.273791	5.153452	30.97586
30.97586	63.75793		32.78207	390.1699	514.7718	614.5336
33.27711	5.108833		34.68077	1027.41	1470.769	402.6834
101.2634	5.119089		393.8926	98.52522	4.912109	7.581867
5.157036	78.00317		3.301947			
01.07.2016	00:00:00	26	467.9089	1.29929	5.41437	31.0564
32.80535	389.4678		513.2097	606.6459	33.45393	5.302368
34.68371	1027.389		1471.556	395.5664	100.1384	5.378284
393.4456	98.53271		4.958979	7.576968	5.411978	78.00467
3.290077						
01.07.2016	00:10:00	27	454.3582	1.270552	5.222803	30.94937
30.94937	63.7481	32.79873	389.5665	514.0494	612.439	33.36375
5.245888	34.63843		1027.36	1471.27	398.209	100.4245
393.1877	98.51691		4.978189	7.587081	5.219887	78.00387
3.29543						

...

This data file and a template that can be used for conversion can be downloaded from [Rosetta-
NERSC-Resources](#) in a folder named Sailbuoy_ArcticOceanAcidification,

Appendix D Example Date/Time formats

Here are some examples of valid date and time formats, and how the date/time field should look for each format.

Date formats

yyyy-MM-dd

2019-11-01

2020-01-05

2021-03-17

yyyy/MM/dd

2019/11/01

2020/01/05

2021/03/17

MM-dd-yyyy

11-01-2019

01-05-2020

03-17-2019

dd-MM-yyyy

01-11-2019

05-01-2020

17-03-2021

yyyy-DDD

2019-305 # November 1 is day 305 in a non leap year.

2020-005

2020-077 # March 17 is day 77 in a leap year.

Time formats

HH:mm:ss # Uppercase HH is 24 hours 00-23, lowercase hh is 12 hours 01-12

00:00:00

02:10:31

13:20:12

HH:mm:ssZ

00:00:00+01 # CET is universal time +01 hour
02:10:31+01
13:20:12+01

HH:mm:ssZ

00:00:00Z # Universal time can be marked as Z or +00 or +0000
02:10:31Z
13:20:12Z

Full Date Time formats

yyyy-MM-dd'T'HH:mm:ss.SSSZ

2019-11-01T00:00:00.000Z
2020-02-23T01:10:01.123+01
2018-12-31T23:59:59.999Z

yyyy-MM-dd'T'HH:mm:ss

2019-11-01T00:00:00
2020-02-23T01:10:01
2018-12-31T23:59:59

yyyy-MM-dd HH:mm:ss

2019-11-01 00:00:00
2020-02-23 01:10:01
2018-12-31 23:59:59

yyyy-MM-dd hh:mm:ss a

2019-11-01 12:00:00 AM
2020-02-23 01:10:01 PM
2018-12-31 11:59:59 PM

Data files and templates that use some of these data formats can be downloaded from [Rosetta-
NERSC-Resources-Alternative timestamps](#).

Appendix E Definition of Date/Time characters

Here is a definition of each character in the date/time formats. Uppercase/lowercase does matter.

* Symbol	Meaning	Presentation	Examples
* -----	-----	-----	-----
* G	era	text	AD
* C	century of era (>=0)	number	20
* Y	year of era (>=0)	year	1996
*			
* x	weekyear	year	1996
* w	week of year	number	27
* e	day of week	number	2
* E	day of week	text	Tuesday; Tue
*			
* y	year	year	1996
* D	day of year	number	189
* M	month of year	month	July; Jul; 07
* d	day of month	number	10
*			
* a	halfday of day	text	PM
* K	hour of halfday (0~11)	number	0
* h	clockhour of halfday (1~12)	number	12
*			
* H	hour of day (0~23)	number	0

* k	clockhour of day (1~24)	number	24
* m	minute of hour	number	30
* s	second of minute	number	55
* S	fraction of second	millis	978
*			
* z	time zone Standard Time; PST	text	Pacific
* Z	time zone offset/id 08:00; America/Los_Angeles	zone	-0800; -
*			
* '	escape for text	delimiter	
* ''	single quote	literal	'

The count of pattern letters determines the format.

Text: If the number of pattern letters is 4 or more, the full form is used; otherwise a short or abbreviated form is used if available.

Number: The minimum number of digits. Shorter numbers are zero-padded to this amount. When parsing, any number of digits are accepted.

Year: Numeric presentation for year and weekyear fields are handled specially. For example, if the count of 'y' is 2, the year will be displayed as the zero-based year of the century, which is two digits.

Month: 3 or over, use text, otherwise use number.

Millis: The exact number of fractional digits. If more millisecond digits are available than specified, the number will be truncated, if there are fewer than specified, then the

number will be zero-padded to the right. When parsing, only the exact number of digits are accepted.

Zone: 'Z' outputs offset without a colon, 'ZZ' outputs the offset with a colon, 'ZZZ' or more outputs the zone id.

Zone names: Time zone names ('z') cannot be parsed.

Any characters in the pattern that are not in the ranges of ['a'..'z'] and ['A'..'Z'] will be treated as quoted text. For instance, characters like ':', '.', ' ', '#', and '?' will appear in the resulting time text even if they are not embraced within single quotes.